

FAT-SOLUBLE VITAMINS

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Small amounts of vitamins are required in the diet to promote growth, reproduction, and health. Vitamins A, D, E, and K are called the fat-soluble vitamins, because they are soluble in organic solvents and are absorbed and transported in a manner similar to that of fats. Vitamin A is required for the maintenance of normal mucous membranes and for normal vision. It occurs naturally only in foods of animal origin, such as liver, butter, whole milk, and egg yolks, but the body converts certain carotenoids, especially β -carotene, to vitamin A. Only 50 of the more than 500 naturally occurring carotenoids have provitamin A activity (Isler et al., 1971; Olson, 1983, 1984). Carotenoids are present in dark-green, leafy vegetables and in yellow and orange vegetables and fruits. In addition, skim milk, margarines, and certain breakfast cereals are fortified with vitamin A. From food composition tables, one can estimate only the total vitamin activity (vitamin A value) but not the quantity of specific carotenoids or retinoids in foods (Beecher and Khachik, 1984). However, researchers are now beginning to add carotenoid values to those in the U.S. Department of Agriculture (USDA) data bank. In 1980 the Recommended Dietary Allowance (RDA) for males 11 years of age and older was 1,000 retinol equivalents (RE), or 5,000 International Units (IU), and for females, 800 RE (4,000 IU) (NRC, 1980). By definition, 1 RE is equal to 1 μg of retinol, 6 μg of β -carotene, or 12 μg of other provitamin A carotenoids. One IU of vitamin A activity is defined as 0.3 μg of retinol and as 0.6 μg of β -carotene. One RE is equal to 3.33 IU of vitamin A activity from retinol and to 10 IU of vitamin A activity from β -carotene. Many food composition tables and most food labels still list vitamin A activity in IU, although the official unit is now RE. The active form of vitamin D promotes intestinal absorption of calcium and phosphorus and influences bone mineralization. Vitamin D occurs in two forms that are equally well utilized in the body. Vitamin D₂ (ergocalciferol) is produced commercially by ultraviolet (UV) irradiation of the plant sterol ergosterol; vitamin D₃ (cholecalciferol) is formed by the action of sunlight on the precursor 7-

dehydrocholesterol in the skin. The human body utilizes both forms of vitamin D by hydroxylating first the 25-position in the liver and then the 1α -position in the kidney, producing the biologically active $1\alpha,25$ -dihydroxycalciferols. Vitamin D occurs naturally only in animal foods such as liver, butter, fatty fish (fish containing high levels of cholesterol or fatty acids as glycerides), and egg yolks. Because natural milk is a poor source, it is fortified with vitamin D to provide 10 μg (400 IU) per quart. The amount of vitamin D formed by exposure of skin to sunlight depends upon the length of the UV irradiation, the intensity, which can be diminished by atmospheric pollution, and skin pigmentation. Aging skin may have diminished capacity to synthesize vitamin D (MacLaughlin and Holick, 1985). Vitamin E is an important antioxidant that is thought to protect polyunsaturated fatty acids from oxidative destruction in cell membranes. Vitamin E activity in foods is due to the presence of tocopherols and tocotrienols—compounds of plant origin. The most important of these is α -tocopherol; less active are β -tocopherol, γ -tocopherol, and α -tocotrienol. Vegetable oils are the richest source of vitamin E. Other good sources include nuts, seeds, whole grains, and wheat germ. The vitamin E content of animal foods is generally low. The RDA for adults is 8 mg of α -tocopherol equivalents (α -TE) or 12 IU for females age 11 and older and 10 mg of α -TE (15 IU) for males age 15 or older. The need for vitamin E is increased if the polyunsaturated fat intake is high, but in the U.S. food supply, foods with high levels of polyunsaturated fatty acids also have a high vitamin E content. Vitamin K is needed in the liver for formation of several blood clotting factors. Vitamin K₁ (phylloquinone) is synthesized by plants, whereas vitamin K₂ homologs (menoquinones) are synthesized by bacteria. The human body can obtain vitamin K from dietary sources as well as through synthesis by the gut microflora. Larger amounts of vitamin K are present in dark-green leafy vegetables; lower levels are found in cereals, dairy products, meats, and fruits. A committee of the Food and Nutrition Board estimated the safe and adequate intake range for adults to be 70 to 140 μg per day. The lower end of that range was based on the assumption that half the daily vitamin K intake is supplied by the diet and that half comes from intestinal synthesis. The higher end of the range represents intake derived entirely from diet. The usual diet of the U.S. population contains 300 to 500 μg per day, and there are no reports of vitamin K deficiency or toxicity in the general population; thus, it has been assumed that dietary intake of vitamin K does not need to be monitored (NRC, 1980).

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